

Both my mom and Eminem have told me that opportunity comes just once in a lifetime, yo. As much as I think those two people are usually spot on, I have to say that I'm a little leery with this one. Can it really be true that there are some other-worldly forces at play, ensuring that an opportunity really is offered just once? Why would they do that? The answer is they wouldn't. Either because they care so little whether someone has more than one opportunity or maybe just because they don't exist. Either way, my stance is that if you miss an opportunity, just relax and another should be along soon. And if you want to get proactive about it, well that's even better. This isn't to say that you should encourage your lethargy to take on a greater role than it already has. No, that's not the case at all.

Although, there is most certainly an endless supply of opportunity, you should always go ahead and take advantage if you can. That's why, contrary to what Mrs. Reagan would recommend, I say, never say no! While this personal policy has certainly landed me in a couple of pickles that I would prefer I wouldn't have been in, the final tally looks pretty good. [sa game](#)

Take advertising business opportunities, for example. Many people tend to simply close up and tune out their attention when they are presented with an offer like, Make a \$1000 per week and just work part time! Why would you do that? This is a business opportunity and while you may encounter that experience one or two times where you ended up paying a couple hundred bucks to get started and then never heard from your new employer again or maybe your identity was stolen and you lost thousands, you just never know when one will hit. If that reminds you of a negative experience that you endured, know this, you're a stronger person because of it. Now pick yourself up, dust yourself off and take advantage, man, because advertising business opportunities may come several, several, several times in your lifetime, but this one's sitting right in front of you, right now.